

Where are my containers?

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Abstract—During the investigation of the security within a seaport ecosystem it turned out that the communication channels between major players, like shipping lines, terminal operators, customs or a Port Community System, may be open gateways for cyber threats. The trust between players is limited as they are frequently competitors, yet communication if not done in an ad hoc manner often occurs without much provision for confidentiality and integrity.

For container shipment the state of containers is crucial information for several players. The players usually operate their own local databases and exchange state changes of containers via bilateral peer-to-peer communication that may easily lead to inconsistent information. Since blockchains are a promising evolving technology to ensure integrity and accountability, we propose and try out a *blockchain* based replacement for classical databases like those for containers. The challenges of blockchain solutions are confidentiality and global access control. In our prototypical implementation for container tracking, we strongly address role-based and attribute-based access control for multi-tenancy.

Index Terms—blockchain, access control, port community system, maritime industry

I. INTRODUCTION

The shipment of containers is a complex task coordinated by several players with their individual—possibly vulnerable—Information Technology (IT). Also, some legal regulations must be obeyed. Assuming that goods are declared at the customs, exported containers must not be loaded on board a vessel without a verified gross mass (VGM) or without a customs' clearance. Imported containers must not be picked up at terminals without being released by shipping lines. Terminals, shipping lines, and a connecting Port Community System (PCS) usually all run their own container tracking databases with possibly wrong or at least globally inconsistent states of containers that are created inadvertently or in bad faith by in- or outside attackers.

This work is related to TradeLens [1] that handles consignments and shipments via a cloud powered platform. Apart from traditional persistence layers, blockchains in TradeLens

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Fig. 1. Traditional export scenario at a port terminal

are used to address trust challenges with an immutable audit trail like for electronic Bills of Lading (eBL).

In Section II, we describe the traditional shipment of containers and the basic integrity problem. In Section III, we sketch an implementation of a blockchain based on Hyperledger Fabric (HF) [2] for container tracking that also incorporates role-based (RBAC) [3] and attribute-based access control (ABAC) [4] for multi-tenancy as well as confidentiality mechanisms. As further extension also ships and their journeys could be tracked by permissioned blockchains along with containers. Section IV concludes with a summary.

II. CONTAINER SHIPMENTS AT SEA PORTS

The traditional procedure of exporting containers works as follows. Initially, an exporter needs to declare the goods to be exported to the customs and to contact a shipping line for the shipment. The shipping line provides containers to be packed. Packed containers are transported—usually by trucks—to the terminal. After a container has been delivered to the terminal, the PCS is informed via an ICU (Content: container arrived at terminal) message and the shipping line via a CODECO (Content: container arrived at terminal) message as shown in Figure 1. The port authority is informed if containers contain dangerous goods. The PCS presents containers to the customs in order to obtain clearances for these containers. For a clearance the goods within containers must have been declared. In a few cases customs may physically inspect containers. After customs' clearance the PCS informs the

terminal and the shipping line. Only cleared containers may be loaded on board a vessel at the terminal. After loading, sailing and unloading a similar procedure applies to the destination terminal that is omitted here for brevity. Before an imported container may be collected, it must have been released by the shipping line.

Problem Description

The problem of this peer-to-peer communication is that a single event, namely the Gate-In action and the customs' clearance, is communicated several times, i.e. two times in Figure 1, and no guarantees exist that these messages are identical, disregarding format changes. The problem here is integrity as known from the children's game telephone. Each child relies on the information it quietly received from one neighbor and passes it slightly modified to its other neighbor leading to a final message funnily related to the initial message. Without monitoring, players may easily become dishonest, i.e., maybe even for minor advantages like saving fees.

Depending on the bilateral communication channels and partners, transmitted information may also be intercepted, manipulated or suppressed leading to different perceptions of the players about the states of their containers. Furthermore, access control is at most enforced by the good will of the individual players.

III. A BLOCKCHAIN IMPLEMENTATION

In Section III-A, we give a brief overview of the used framework before we introduce life cycle states of containers in Section III-B. In Section III-C, we describe our blockchain solution for the above problem and Section III-D presents the implemented example blockchain net.

A. Framework Overview

HF is a modular open-source development platform for permissioned blockchains. Compared to public blockchains (like bitcoin) that use proof-of-work, *consensus* in HF is far more efficient and forks can be avoided. Transactions and new *blocks* are created within seconds, thus establishing *immediate finality*.

A *blockchain net* is run by a consortium and provides so-called *channels* as *virtual blockchains*. The organizations run *peers* that hold physical copies of the blockchain, the actual *ledgers*. Ledgers are accessed by *smart contracts* (or *chaincode*) creating *transactions* that are initiated by external applications from authorized participants (having certificates).

One choice of consensus in HF is achieved by *ordering*. Every transaction needs to obtain sufficiently many *endorsements* from other peers. The ordering service checks signed endorsements, orders transactions, creates new blocks and propagates them to all peers.

The ledger can be viewed as a distributed key-value store. As unique keys, we suggest container numbers and as values container attributes where the current state of a container should be one important attribute and the organization(s) responsible for a container be another.

Fig. 2. Container states

Transactions that are part of a block describe *incremental changes* of container attributes. Peers usually keep a state database for direct access that can be constructed—or reconstructed after a restart—by applying all the transactions from the ledger to an initial state.

B. Container States for Workflow and Access Control

Access control is implemented in chaincode. Only organizations with certain roles or organizations responsible for specific containers, also called *owners* of containers, are allowed to change the state of a container. The state changes allowed are subject to role assignments.

The possible states of a container are basically values of an enumeration type and possible state changes are described by a lifecycle or finite state diagram as shown in Figure 2. These states are more than a rough physical location, the states are supposed to track the global actual workflow regarding the necessary processing steps of the various players.

For a consignment, a shipping line would *initialize* a container by organizing an empty container to be packed (by an exporter) and delivered to a specific terminal. Containers reaching the gate of a terminal change their life cycle state to *delivered*. A PCS would observe delivered containers and *present* them to the customs. Eventually, omitting exceptions, the container would become *cleared* and could be *loaded* onto a vessel. At the destination terminal the container would be *unloaded*, *released*, and *collected*. After the consignment is *completed*, the lifecycle could be repeated.

Note, that the exact physical position at the terminal or onboard a vessel is unknown. In fact, exact physical positions would be interesting data for smugglers that should not be stored on a blockchain. Apart from physical container properties, like dimensions or devices for ventilation or controlling temperatures, also non-confidential information about the goods is stored on the blockchain.

Fig. 3. Changed export scenario via a Blockchain

Along with the container states the players responsible for a container are stored as container attributes. Initially, the creating shipping line is responsible for a container and would choose the responsible terminal(s). However, shipping lines can only set the state of their containers to *created*. Later on, only the terminal for export can change the state from *created* to *delivered* (as Gate-In action) and from *cleared* to *loaded* (when loading). Changing other container attributes, in particular after the presentation to the customs, is not permitted.

C. Container Tracking using a Blockchain

The integrity problem, described in Section II, can now be solved by recording a single event once and visible for all in a central data store like in a blockchain. The corresponding workflow is shown in Figure 3.

The Gate-In event is now stored only once on the blockchain by setting a container's state to *delivered* and this state can be read by the corresponding shipping line and the PCS in whatever format they like. The interpretation of data from the blockchain is now done by the readers and not by the sender.

Migrating Roles within a Blockchain Net

As further simplification we join the roles of a PCS, the customs, and the port authority into a single PCS role. By this design only the PCS would need to be a major member of the blockchain net. Customs and the port authority would not be affected. The PCS would inform the port authority about containers with dangerous goods as before and the PCS would forward the customs' clearance decisions by setting a container's state to *cleared*.

At a later stage, customs and the port authority could join the blockchain net. The port authority could then directly inspect *delivered* containers with dangerous goods, and customs could directly set the clearance state, while the PCS would no longer be responsible for these tasks. (The PCS still does the qualified presentation to support the customs.) As is typical for RBAC, the permissions associated to roles usually change as new roles are introduced.

Supporting Multitenancy

For a concrete seaport area, only a single PCS (customs and port authority) but multiple competing terminals and shipping

Fig. 4. Example blockchain net with five organization

lines need to be considered. A mere RBAC model is not sufficient to describe the different interests and permissions of competing users having the same role. In order to support *multitenancy* [5] of terminals and shipping lines, that are the tenants, we use ABAC. It is the most flexible model, subsumes RBAC as roles can be viewed as attributes, but it is also complicated and thus error-prone. In ABAC, access depends on attributes attached to accessing subjects, accessed objects, and even the context, i.e., time of day or location, of the access. Of course, all these attributes must also be protected and are subject of access control. For our multitenancy we restrict access of shipping lines and terminals to those containers they are responsible for. As attribute we use the identity of shipping lines and terminals. The identity of all members of a permissioned blockchain is known and provable via certificates, whereas the blockchain itself securely stores the identity of the responsible tenants as container attributes. Permissions like state changes can then be granted based on comparisons of these identity attributes.

D. Example Blockchain Net

In order to demonstrate the roles and multitenancy we have set up a blockchain net, as shown in Figure 4, with five players for the three roles: a PCS and two competing terminals and shipping lines each, named *PCS*, *terminal1*, *terminal2*, *carrier1*, and *carrier2*.

The network with role-dependent chaincode and an application have been established in analogy to the samples given for HF [6]. The application (implemented using Angular [7]) that can only trigger chaincode transactions (implemented in Go [8]) provides a view to the container blockchain that is very similar to a traditional database view.

Figure 5 shows a contrived container table as the authenticated *PCS*, displayed in the top-right corner, would see it. The application layer hides the fact that the last two columns are not part of the blockchain but *private data* as supported by HF. Detailed information about the cargo and exact container locations are supposed to be confidential, yet this private data may be securely shared in later stages when customs or a port authority become members of the blockchain.

The important columns are those that show the responsible shipping line (or carrier) and the export¹ terminal.

¹We disregard here the import terminal at the destination that would become responsible after containers have been *loaded*.

Container	VGM	Type	State	Destination	Carrier	Terminal	Cargo	Location
ABCD1234567	20T	20G1	delivered	Antwerp	carrier1	terminal1	Coal	A5
BCDE2345678	22T	20G0	cleared	Bremen	carrier2	terminal1	Stone	B3
HDJC1231239	35T	45B3	created	Valencia	carrier1	terminal1	Logs	R22
JFUE1235433	32T	45U6	delivered	Le Havre	carrier2	terminal2	Iron	I4
JKAC2459234	52T	42R1	created	Amsterdam	carrier2	terminal2	Cereals	G17
KJUZ8574329	50T	42T5	delivered	Hamburg	carrier1	terminal2	Oxygen	U7
NKJS7384921	30T	42T2	created	London	carrier1	terminal1	Fish	D12
POAD0978567	45T	42T6	cleared	Barcelona	carrier2	terminal1	Copper	F3
QWER1231233	32T	42R1	delivered	Bergen	carrier2	terminal2	Wine	C4
WXYZ1234567	26T	22G0	created	Rotterdam	carrier1	terminal2	Plastic	H7

Fig. 5. The view of the *PCS* on containers

Implemented Access Restrictions

In contrast to the *PCS*, shipping lines and terminals cannot see private data but can only view those containers they are responsible for. The corresponding views for the exemplary players, *carrier2* and *terminal2*, are shown in Figure 6 and 7 respectively. A redundant column for the carrier or terminal that would contain the authenticated player itself as a constant is no longer shown for an improved view.

The screenshots do not reveal that access control is actually implemented by chaincode. The application layer only reflects access restrictions to provide a better user experience. Any self-written application can only call transactions defined by chaincode for the authenticated identity. It is the chaincode that enforces any access restriction for an identity!

The implemented application does not only show the relevant container entries but also supports to trigger state or

Container	VGM	Type	State	Destination	Terminal
BCDE2345678	22T	20G0	cleared	Bremen	terminal1
JFUE1235433	32T	45U6	delivered	Le Havre	terminal2
JKAC2459234	52T	42R1	created	Amsterdam	terminal2
POAD0978567	45T	42T6	cleared	Barcelona	terminal1
QWER1231233	32T	42R1	delivered	Bergen	terminal2

Fig. 6. The view of *carrier2*

Container	VGM	Type	State	Destination	Carrier
JFUE1235433	32T	45U6	delivered	Le Havre	carrier2
JKAC2459234	52T	42R1	created	Amsterdam	carrier2
KJUZ8574329	50T	42T5	delivered	Hamburg	carrier1
QWER1231233	32T	42R1	delivered	Bergen	carrier2
WXYZ1234567	26T	22G0	created	Rotterdam	carrier1

Fig. 7. The view of *terminal2*

attribute changes (by clicking on an entry for testing purposes). Only these changes, if considered valid by the chaincode, lead to new blocks on the blockchain. Any transaction on the blockchain is signed by the identity that initiated it. Thus, identities can be made liable for their changes.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The presented implementation allows to further investigate the replacement of traditional databases, i.e., for containers or ships, by blockchains in order to make workflows in the seaport ecosystem more secure. The major advantages of a permissioned blockchain is *accountability* and *integrity*. Furthermore, the information is shared within a consortium and not controlled by an organization that must be trusted. Via chaincode, *global* access control can be enforced. With local databases, access can at most be controlled on an organizational basis.

Comparing our proposed container blockchain with the current situation where state changes are only communicated with delay to a few partners, the signed transactions ensure unique consistent states of containers and increase the likelihood that these states correspond to the actual physical reality as signing identities may be made liable otherwise. We showed how to implement RBAC and ABAC/multitenancy policies that apply to the whole consortium.

The blockchain is supposed to establish a catalog of all containers known by a consortium. Not all attributes of containers are stored on the blockchain. HF supports *private data* to be securely shared by a few organizations only—subject to a policy. Organizations are free to store additional information of containers for their own purposes. Containers are a basic *entity* (with container numbers as keys) of a larger entity-relation diagram. Only important, basically non-secret, and non-bulk attributes are transparently stored on the blockchain to provide a consistent view on containers for all members of a maritime ecosystem. Goods or ships could be further entities.

A couple of issues remain to be discussed for a blockchain solution:

- Our HF implementation used the default policies for endorsements and consensus. More meaningful policies than just sufficient support by any members should be investigated. Proof-of-Authority may be an option for consensus.
- A permissioned blockchain relies on a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) for digitally signing endorsements and transactions. There are various ways to reuse or establish a trustworthy PKI and its certificate authorities (CAs).
- The chaincode that controls the access to the blockchain is critical software that needs to be agreed upon. Changes to the chaincode require also consensus.
- An implemented access control policy may be hard to understand for a security manager by mere code inspection. A policy should be given in a descriptive way. The current state of the art for specifying ABAC policies is XACML [9]. In any case an automatic translation from a

readable specification to executable chaincode would be desirable.

- From an economic viewpoint, the possibly huge number of replicated copies of the blockchain is unattractive. For mere backup purpose a few reliable copies would be better suited. Furthermore, shipping lines and terminals are only allowed to access a small proportion of the containers. Compared with a distributed database, only a subset of the required data would need to be replicated, temporarily.
- The described visibility restrictions implemented by chaincode transactions can be circumvented by directly inspecting the blockchain that is distributed to the peers of the members. Blockchains are inherently transparent and thus pose confidentiality problems. Additional legal, organizational, or technical measures should protect the raw blockchain data, but evil administrators may prevail. Therefore, personal or otherwise sensitive data does not belong on blockchains!
- Transactions on a blockchain can never be deleted. It is unclear if this causes scalability problems in the long run. If it does, one may think of discontinuing a blockchain and starting a new one that would reflect a more recent past.
- Establishing a consortium around a single PCS for a local port area bears the problem of how to cooperate with other port areas. In particular shipping lines attend many other terminals. A single world-wide container blockchain would be ideal, but maybe this is an unrealistic aim.

With our implemented proposal we provided a practical testing ground for a possible transition from traditional local

databases to blockchains with global access control in order to make some workflows more secure with respect to integrity.

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